

THE ROLE OF THE NATIONAL IDEA IN ENSURING SPIRITUAL AND IDEOLOGICAL SECURITY

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Abstract: This article examines the role of national-spiritual security in ensuring national security. The article also analyzes the growing number of threats to national and moral security and the issue of its prevention.

Keywords: human history, progresses, development, ideological threats, spirituality, culture, ideological immunity, values, reforms

The history testifies that human history is the history of ideas. Today, as society progresses, various threats to the nation instead of diminishing, on the contrary, are becoming more and more intense. In the 21st century, a number of countries in the world have reached the stage of high development, the people's needs and interests have been met, and prosperity has increased somewhat. But these changes did not prevent spiritual and ideological threats, but led to their further escalation. In fact, economic development does not guarantee moral security. Therefore, it is necessary to search for the prevention factors of human life in such complex conditions and to use them effectively to eliminate various threats.

Today, the high development of science, technology and technology attracts people and the nation, and spiritual and ideological aggression is carried out through seemingly safe tools - ideas, ideology, spirituality and culture. The national idea appears as an important factor in preventing this danger in society. When it is inculcated into the consciousness, thinking, spirituality and morals of the members of the society to the extent that it does not leave room for ideas contrary to its interests in the daily life of the members, spiritual and ideological security is formed and the stable development of the society is observed.

Therefore, in such conditions, the harmonious development and consistent improvement of the national idea and ideology will have practical significance in protecting the nation from ideological influences. Of course, moral-ideological security means that nations are free from harmful threats to their spirituality.

An important factor in ensuring the security of the nation depends on the strength of moral and ideological immunity. The growing number of threats in this direction makes its prevention more complicated. The forces behind inhumane goals are masterfully using destructive ideas and ideologies to achieve their heinous goals. Naturally, in response to them, this situation demands the development and improvement of ideas and ideologies that serve their essence, humanity, goodness and creativity, and serve to preserve national values and ensure the security of the nation. In such a system of ideas, the national idea is of particular importance. Because it embodies not only the unique customs, traditions and values of the nation, but also its consciousness, thinking, and experiences of living.

Another opportunity of the national idea to ensure moral and ideological security is that it embodies the spirit of the nation. It plays an important role in forming a sense of belonging to the reforms in the minds of young people and in developing their activity. Patriotic feelings will be strong in the minds and hearts of young people who have mastered the great spiritual heritage of their ancestors and learned from the experiences they have gained during their lives. Because it is the national idea that represents the main directions of the development of people, nations, peoples, societies and social groups and political forces, based on past experiences, serves to know the needs of the future, to determine the possibilities of development.

In particular, factors such as national consciousness, national identity, historical memory, national heritage and national mentality occupy a leading place in the system of the national idea. The important aspect of the national idea is that it organizes the representatives of the nation as a theoretical basis for realizing the national interests, protecting them and ensuring the nation's perspective.

The types and forms of security in the life of society are extremely diverse, and spiritual and ideological security has a special place in their system. Security in its broadest sense encompasses all forms. After all, if the moral-ideological security of the nation is ensured, its other forms are also ensured in some sense. Because all of them are formed not at the same time, but at different times and for different reasons.

National security cannot be imagined without a national idea. Because only the national idea turns the nation into a real material entity. In this sense, the existence of the nation means the existence of its own idea. The very existence of a national idea means the need to protect it. One of the most important factors in ensuring national security is national spirituality.

Spirituality manifests itself as a powerful force only in the “national image”. Because it embodies the nation's identity, customs, traditions, values, spirit, honor and pride. Without them, spirituality is unthinkable and remains only a theoretical concept. All of the above-mentioned aspects of the nation's spirituality not only give strength to the nation, but at the same time, it is a fortress that protects it from any threats.

The fact that the issue of spirituality has become one of the most urgent tasks in our society is the product of this need. After all, the factor that truly makes a nation a nation, unites and unites, is national identity! In order not to lose our national spirituality, age-old values and traditions, we need a national idea like water and air.

It is known that today in the world there is a sharp struggle and competition, and the conflict of interests is increasing. The processes of globalization are creating new opportunities for humanity, as well as unexpected problems. Threats and dangers against national identity and moral values are increasing. Thinking only of oneself, looking lightly at work and family, and consumerism are masterfully instilled in the minds of people, especially young people, in different ways.

Threats such as terrorism, extremism, transnational and cyber-crime, human trafficking, and drug trafficking are increasing. In some regions, instability is

deliberately created and the mood of protest is growing. In such a dangerous situation, it is necessary to be alert and alert, to live thinking of the peace of our people and the interests of our country.

It should be noted that the system of responsibility for protecting the nation is comprehensive and includes economic, social-political, military, spiritual-educational and ecological spheres. Each of them has its own unique functions, tasks and potential for influence, and neglecting any one of them constitutes neglect of the responsibility of protecting the nation. On the ground of this indifference, there is moral and ideological weakness in the representatives of the nation.

The responsibility of protecting the nation cannot be fully strengthened without addressing this weakness. To be more specific, in the system of strengthening the responsibility of protecting the nation, it is necessary to consistently develop and consistently improve the national spirituality, which draws strength from the national idea and becomes the moral-spiritual basis for moral-ideological security. Thus, it is correct to say that the main link in the system of strengthening the responsibility of protecting the nation is the national idea, the provision of national-spiritual security.

The power of the national idea in the minds of the representatives of the nation to protect themselves from various threats, its real threat to the nation is expressed in the extent to which it is connected with the family, its goals and objectives. The provision of national-spiritual security is also expressed in the public efforts of the representatives of the nation to protect their native language, customs, traditions, and protect them from all kinds of external and internal harmful threats. It is necessary to form and strengthen the feelings of self-preservation in the mind and worldview of the representatives of the nation, and above all, as we mentioned above, to ensure national-spiritual security.

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